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Developing Creativity among Engineering Design Students

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ABSTRACT

As one of key drivers to solve real-life problems in practice of sustainable innovation, creativity has been argued as an important skill that engineering graduates have to master. This paper will mainly focus on 1) how to understand the concept of creativity and its relevance with sustainability in engineering design, and 2) as the educators, how we can provide basic conditions to recognise, develop, and assess creativity among engineering design students. The two focuses will further drive us to discuss a case of an education program of Medialogy at Aalborg University (AAU) in Denmark. Briefly, this paper contributes to bringing together with areas of creativity, engineering design, and engineering education, which also indicate that it has both theoretical and practical significances.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability and Engineering Education, Engineering Skills

Keywords: creativity, engineering design, engineering education, sustainability, creativity assessment

INTRODUCTION

Recently, creativity has become a crucial issue for human-resource management in both academic research and industry. It is increasingly recognised that creativity and innovation are required to deal with changing circumstances in education and society as a whole [1]. So, the universities are increasingly expected to provide more opportunities that foster and nurture creativity in engineering students. Engineering students need creative minds to meet the advancing goal of engineering profession, design new products or systems and improve existing ones for the benefit of humankind [2]

The arguments that engineering design students require creativity also involve the consideration of developing sustainability [3]. In engineering design, it is necessary to add customers' requirements related to sustainability. Both the development of a product and making it sustainable requires the involvement of creativity into product design. So during the product lifecycle, the engineers must be able to be creative in all areas of the process. The creativity not only makes them more competitive than before but also favours more sustainability with innovation for possible solutions to many of the problems [4].

Following the above, this paper emphasises the necessity of developing creativity among engineering students and deepens the understanding of creativity and its assessment methods. This further implies us to show the plan of curriculum design in an educational program of Mediaology at Aalborg University (AAU) in Denmark. Therefore, this paper not only contributes to a theoretical bridging creativity and engineering design education in one framework, but also provide practical implications to educators for recognising and assessing creativity among engineering design students.

1 WHAT IS CREATIVITY?

The creativity has many perspectives of seeing. Creativity can be defined simply as a generation of a new and useful idea [5], [6]. In other words, Creativity is the conceptualization, the schematization and the execution of ideas [7], [8].

Therefore, the meaning is subjective to be measured at different cultures and backgrounds. According to Zhou [9], creativity has to see in an integral mode, as the integration of knowledge and skills. It could be effective to assess people to selection, management or classification purposes. The interaction between persons could see at the interpersonal, the group, and the socio-cultural level. Both individual and group can produce a tangible product, material or immaterial that is useful according to with the social contexts [10], [11]. Consequently, creativity could recognise by the people, the product, the process and the environment. That approach to assessing creativity is known as the 4P's of creativity, which means Person, Process, Product and Place.

2 CREATIVITY AND SUSTIANABILITY IN ENGINEERING DESIGN

In engineering design, creativity has its significances of developing sustainability. A new idea always has to be tested or use to be a real "idea" that is also useful. In a broad sense, we may view creativity as a pathway to develop sustainability. While sustainability refers to the design of human and industrial systems "to ensure that humankind's use of natural resources and cycles do not lead to diminished quality of life due either to losses in future economic opportunities or adverse impacts on social conditions, health and the environment"[12, p. 5315].

Furthermore, we can use the principles of precautionary and the prevention when to assess sustainability that also has effects on creativity. The precautionary principle is a strategy to address uncertainties in risk management [13]. This principle establishes that uncertainty determines the measures that must be taken to avoid damages to society and the environment. Therefore, engineers must take actions before damage can occur. Therefore, cautions include wider assumptions, recognise weaknesses and points where there is not knowledge, uncertainties, advantages and disadvantages, stakeholder recommendations, use of specialists, documents, and the real operating conditions. Also, engineers have to think of short- and long-term monitoring programs [14], [15]. The principle of prevention states that if the consequences and probability or occurrence of any activity is known, measures should be taken to avoid further damage to the environment or society.

According to Cucuzzella [4], the precautionary mode is typical of the stages of the formulation of the problem and involve reflection in action. The prevention mode is for stages involves technical knowledge while developing the solution of the problem. At the stage of a problem, the setting should appear requirements that include uncertainty. The way of the problem is addressed, and the different alternatives of presenting it are related to creativity. Furthermore, creativity promotes the search for various alternatives. The preventionary approach is oriented toward various action alternatives, reconstructing existing social and cultural elements; while the precautionary approach uses both instrumental models and critically constructed models. So the two principles have opposite effects on creativity in problem-solving and problem-setting contexts.

However, to Cucuzzella [4], also argued that the two principles of precaution and prevention coexist within a problem-solving and problem-setting model of thinking. That makes it possible to reveal at least four tensions that help to understand how creativity is impacted in the context of designing for sustainability. The four tensions are: (1) analogical/logical conceptualization, (2) epistemological/methodological uncertainty, (3) interpretive/analytic comparability, and (4) universal/contextual relevance of proposal. These four tensions comprise a system for judgment as they each address a major element of design thinking.

3 ASSESSING CREATIVITY IN ENGINEERING DESIGN EDUCATION

According to the literature [16], there is a great deal of controversy about the meaning of the word creativity, particularly in a university setting. It shows that some disciplines have been involved:

- 1) Psychology has focused on the individual's creativity and tried to identify the cognitive capacities and traits of personality that make up a creative person.
- 2) Social psychology has studied the process of creativity as an interaction within a given context.
- 3) Sociology (and organisation theory) has emphasised creativity as an environmental process and studied efficient communication networks made up of prominent personalities with broad and deep knowledge.

Törnkvist [16] also argued it is important to recognise which approach mentioned in the above when we develop and assess students' creativity in engineering education. For example, if one believes that creativity is constituted by a set of traits of personality only, testing for those traits of personality only, testing for those traits at entry level would seem to be a necessary and sufficient means of ensuring future creativity. If one believes that the social context has influences on creativity, as suggested by Amabile

and Pillemer [17], creativity could be taught, learned, practised and developed, and everyone has potential to be more creative than before through positive influences of educational environments on developing creative ideas and learning methods of developing creativity. So, in educational methods based on collaboration, the assessing of creativity is view as a result of a process, at the end of an individual or group work.

In engineering design, assessing creativity has been focused on from a product perspective [18]–[21]. Creative engineering designers are those who can explore and scrutinise the available data or information and generate novel solutions to specific engineering problems or the production of a unique product are demanded in work places and markets [21]–[23]. The following four aspects of defining a creative product should be considered [23]

- 1) Relevance and effectiveness: the product solves the problem it was intended to solve.
- 2) Novelty: the product is original and ‘surprising’.
- 3) Elegance: the product is ‘beautiful’ or pleasing, and goes beyond a simple mechanical solution. And
- 4) Generalizability: the product is broadly applicable - it can be transferred to situations other than the present one and opens up perspectives for solving other problems.

Furthermore, as little engineering work is solitary, it is increasingly being recognised as a collaborative problem-solving process where is also the main context of creativity among engineers [23]. Also, ‘responsibility’ should be involved, which highlights the designers must be able and willing to think about their ethical liability for the consequences when the creative products are applied in practice [24]. For example, the relevance of sustainability with engineering design has been emphasised in this paper.

Also, to better assess creativity from the perspective of the product, observers have to review both the process explanation for the developing the product and the final product. There could involve many aspects, such as the problem formulation, user requirements and preliminary, and final specifications. Furthermore, the observers have to deal with accidental aspects (e.g., unintentional solutions). A student was tacitly explaining in a special session on a report facilitating the observation process.

4 DEVELOPING CREATIVITY IN ENGINEERING DESIGN EDUCATION

In the following, we take an example of the curriculum plan in a student programme of Medialogy at Aalborg University (AAU) in Denmark to show how engineering design education may provide necessary conditions for creativity. It should be noted here that AAU has a long tradition of an educational model of Problem-Based Learning (PBL). Students in Medialogy will have a ten-semester study period. Every semester, each student group should finish a project report which indicates their design processes and design products in solving real-life problems.

The Bachelor's degree in Medialogy at AAU begins with the students getting an insight into basic Information technology, Communication, New Media, Programming and the completion of a problem-oriented project. In the first year, the students in project teams analyse and solve a problem within the area Human-Computer Interaction. They draw up a problem formation and qualify a research question where they will be able to apply their knowledge and skills in mathematics, programming and interaction design. *Fig. 1* shows the detailed description of learning objectives of student projects.

<p>Title: Human-computer interaction</p>
<p>15 ECT</p>
<p>Objectives: After completing the Project module, the student shall be able to demonstrate knowledge, skills and competencies in how design, develop and evaluate and artefact.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Knowledge</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe new form of interaction with the real world, data sources, and/or physical/virtual models (understanding) • Explain how human computer confluence can enhance the foundations for future applications of societal value (understanding) • Explain the methods for planning and developing and IT application (understanding) • Explain the iterative nature of interaction design (understanding)
<p style="text-align: center;">Skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applied the human center design approach in the contest of use, design, development and evaluation of a new interface (understanding) • Design, plan, organise and conduct user needs study of a target group (synthesis) • Analyse how a chosen target group interacts in a real world context of use with similar media products or artefacts and apply this to novel designs through, e.g., scenarios and storyboards, and later with early prototypes • Apply methods, tools and theories to allow people to explore and augment human interaction capabilities and awareness in action and interaction. • Synthesize technical requirements specifications as a basis for developing a media technology project • Design and implement a simple artefact based on fundamental object-oriented programming (COP) strategies, models and development environments (application) • Prepare and perform standardised testing of an artefact with the target user group (not a convenience sample) or domain experts and analyse and discuss the findings (application)
<p style="text-align: center;">Competencies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply the gained experiences with project management to the future course of study (evaluation) • Evaluate the ethical perspective of engineering and science and discuss implications of a responsible professional practice (analysis) • Explain basic quantitative results with descriptive statistics in writing and in figures (application)

Fig. 1. Learning Objectives in Medialogy

So the students must create a model of the problem and include relevant concepts, theory and methods for analysis and assessment of possible sustainable solutions. As part of the solution, the students must develop an artefact, which has to be documented in the project report.

For example, The Intelligent Ashtray shown in *Fig. 2* is one of the students' projects in the 2nd semester. The overall theme of the semester is garbage in Denmark. The students first look at a lot of different areas to work their way towards finding a solvable problem in regards to garbage and dogged into which matters could be resolved. Then

one group of students are very interested in issues of smokers. The issue is not merely that people throw the cigarette butts to irritate other persons, but rather another issue in finding places to dispose of it. Some people state that they do not recognise cigarette butts as litter, while others state that most ashtrays are full. Whatever the reason may be for not disposing of the cigarette butts correctly, the students decided to try and count this problem Based on the problem analysis. Finally, a problem formation was created by the students:

How do we motivate our primary group, the smokers, to reduce their littering of cigarette butts and in turn create awareness for our secondary group, the non-smokers, in the city of Aalborg?

This project aims to solve the problem formation with an interactive ashtray, with a design that would make it easy to spot. The ashtray has an info-screen, which seeks to change the user's perspectives in littering through information printed on-screen.

Fig. 2. The Intelligent Ashtray

The project includes a full implementation and product test. It showed, that "The Intelligent Astray" in the city of Aalborg had an impact on both the primary and the secondary target groups, in that it changed the motivations of the smokers to use the ashtray and made the non-smokers aware of the issues surrounding cigarette littering.

From the above case, we can learn that in Medialogy, sustainability has been an important element embedded in the curriculum design. Meanwhile, the product perspective creativity has been highlighted when the students are required to solve real-life problems; the criteria for assessing creativity discussed previously including relevance and effectiveness, novelty, elegance, and generalizability have also been encouraged to be reached among the students in the process of their design. Also, AAU is a supportive educational environment to develop creativity, as it has core principles such as group work, student-centered learning, and the shift from teaching to facilitation, which meets the requirements of fostering a creative learning atmosphere and students' active participation in creative activities.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper addresses the issues of developing creativity among engineering design students. These issues involve how to rethink what the concept of creativity means in the field of engineering design and its relevance with sustainability, and how to

recognise and assess creativity among engineering design students. It is clear that only when educators have the strong awareness of developing creative teaching and learning, and when they can understand and recognise the needs and the particular characteristics of creativity in engineering design, the supportive curriculum design and educational environment can be accordingly developed. So a case of a student programme of Medialogy at AAU discussed may provide a practical example of how to integrate creativity into curriculums in engineering design education, which also provide implications for other engineering institutions around the world.

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